

COMPARATIVE STUDY ON INTERNAL AND EXTERNAL RELEASE AGENTS – EVALUATION OF PROCESS PARAMETER VARIATION ON DEMOLDING STRESSES

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ABSTRACT

The use of Internal Release Agents is one of the most promising strategies to reduce cycle time and therefore production costs in Resin Transfer Molding processes. Hereby, the Internal Release agent is mixed into the resin system. During the injection and the cure-cycle, the Internal Release Agent drifts to the mold surface and builds a passivating layer. This strategy supersedes the need for release coatings and thereby discards the coating of the mold surface by an external release agent before injection. The occurring effects are dependent on the process conditions during the injection and the cure-cycle. However, the knowledge of influencing factors and occurring mechanisms is restricted. Today the process parameters for internal release agents are mostly set by trial and error.

In this investigation the demolding stress is examined with a tensile test. Therefore, a pick-up plate is designed to manufacture tensile-test specimens and the dependency of the demolding stress on four process parameters is analyzed: amount of release agent, temperature of mold-surface, number of demoldings, and the kind of a reinforcement structure. Accordingly, the trials show four results. First, a higher amount of internal release agent lessens the demolding forces, whereas a repeated coating with external release agents does not improve the release behavior. Second, a higher temperature leads to lower demolding forces. Thirdly, the number of demoldings do not show an effect on the demolding stress. Last, differences in the demolding stresses are detected by a comparison of three glass fiber architectures even though the reinforcement structures are not in contact with the surface of the tooling.

1 INTRODUCTION

In the last decades lightweight aspects gained more importance in the construction and transport industry. This opened composite materials a broad field of application since they offer high weight specific mechanical properties. Fiber Reinforced Plastics are therefore integrated as structural components in cars, airplanes, bridges, or wind turbine blades. Even though high volume production today is often limited by labor and are therefore cost intensive manufacturing processes [1].

Resin Transfer Molding (RTM) processes offer a high potential for automation and therefore short cycle times. Hereby a dry fabric is draped in the final part contour and placed into a solid mold. The cavity of the mold is filled with a resin system during the injection. Then the part is cured under a heat and pressure load. Finally the part is de-molded and additionally post-processed if necessary.

Today a lot of research focuses on the improvement of resin-fiber adhesion. Contrary to that, the effects necessary for the adhesion of the composite part from the mold surface is mostly neglected [2,3] although there is a demand to improve the process. For example, external release coatings have to be applied manually on the mold surface prior to the injection. Furthermore, a minimum of three coatings are required in the aerospace industry to ensure sufficient coating of the mold.

Hence, Internal Release Agents (IRA) are an alternative to the time consuming and error-prone processing of these External Release Agents (ERA). Hereby the IRA, mostly fatty acid esters, metal stearates, or waxes, are dissolved in the resin system during mixing and distributed in the mold during injection [4]. The following mechanisms responsible for the adhesion are still uncertain [3,5]. Jennings describes a theory, that migration of metallic salts such as stearates of the composite or polymer

surface result in the formation of a fatty monolayer between the cured part and the tool surface [6]. Fletcher, on the other hand, focuses on the change in solubility of the mold release agent between the uncured and the cured state, causing an incompatibility at the surface and forming a surface level molecular separation layer [7]. To understand this phenomenon, the factors helping to achieve good adhesion are essential [2].

This study investigates the demolding stress dependent upon a selection of process parameters. For this, three steps are performed. First, a pick-up plate (see Figure 1) is designed to build tensile-test specimens representing the demolding stresses. Second, a step-by-step routine is developed to ensure the reproducibility of the results. Thirdly, process parameter are varied to display their effect on the demolding stress: The amount of IRA is varied between 1.5% and 3.0% respective of the pure resin mass; the mold temperature is set to 50°C and 100°C; the trend over four demolding processes with IRA is recorded, and the influence of reinforcement structures are evaluated with three different fabrics. With the results, these process parameters can be adjusted to optimize the effect of IRA.

2 MATERIALS AND TEST SETUP

2.1 MATRIX MATERIALS

The first epoxy resin system (RSI) is a bisphenol-A-(epichlorhydrin) resin ‘EPIKOTE RESIN MGS RIMR 135’ combined with an alkyletheramine hardener ‘EPIKURE CURING AGENT MGS RIMH 1366’ produced by Momentive that is mainly used for the production of wind turbine blades. The mixing ratio is 100:30 by mass percentage. The second epoxy resin (RS II) is a bisphenol-A-(epichlorhydrin) resin ‘XB3585’ combined with a diethylenetriamine hardener ‘XB 3458’ produced by Huntsman that is frequently used in the automotive industry. The mixing ratio is 100:19 by mass percentage.

For this investigation one ERA and two IRA were selected. As an ERA ‘Frekote 770-NC’, a standard ERA from Henkel for the aerospace industry is used. The first IRA (IRA I) ‘Ewo Mold 3202’ is produced by KVS Eckert & Woelk. The second IRA (IRA II) ‘PAT-657/BW’ is produced by E. and P. Würtz & Co KG. As most of the IRA, these products are mainly used in applications with a high degree of automation.

2.2 REINFORCEMENT MATERIALS

For the comparison of textile structures, three glass fiber materials were selected (see Table 1).

Abbreviation	Textile structure	Areal weight	Lay-up	FVF (~)
NCF	Bi-Diagonal, Non-Crimp Fabric	610 g/m ²	-45°/+45°/+45°/-45°	35%
PW	Plain Weave	425 g/m ²	90°/0°/0°/90°	48%
NOF	Non-Oriented Fabric	230 g/m ²	-	33%

Table 1: Reinforcement structures of used glass fiber materials

2.3 SAMPLE PICK-UP PLATE

To manufacture the tensile test samples, a pick-up plate (see Figure 1) is designed. It consists of two steel halves, each comprised of six specimen adapters of aluminum with a diameter of 50mm. Thus, six test samples can be manufactured at once. Furthermore, adjustment pins are integrated to ensure the position of the upper and lower specimen adapters to minimize shear forces during the tensile tests. Special attention is given to the parallelism of the specimen adapters and the adjustment to a 1mm gap-size by the design.

Figure 1: Pick-up plate with 6 specimen adapter

2.3 TEST SETUP

The tests are performed in a 100kN load cell of a Hegewald & Peschke tensile test machine under controlled temperature conditions of 23°C (+/- 2°C). The specimen adapters are screwed in the machine adapters (see Figure 2).

Figure 2: Load cell with a resin system specimen

To calculate the load from the force signal of the tensile test machine, the specimen surface area is detected visually and measured in an image processing software (Stream Motion).

3 EXPERIMENTAL DESCRIPTION

First, the specimen adapters are ground in a Struers TegraForce-5 polishing machine with a P500 sand paper. By this, a contamination of the surface by earlier tests can be excluded and comparable conditions between the tests can be assumed. After this preparation, the specimen adapters are screwed into the pick-up plate and subsequently cleaned, using 2-propanol to remove organic contamination. For the test series II, III and IV the resin is heated to 25°C in an oven to copy a RTM injection set-up with a temperature guidance for the resin, in test series I the resin is not heated. To manufacture one batch of six specimens, 100g resin and 30g hardener (RS I) respectively 19g hardener (RS II) are

mixed by hand. The amount of IRA is referred to the pure resin amount since in most processes, the IRA is added to the pure resin before mixing with the hardener. Approximately 1,5 g of resin system is added on every specimen adapter. After curing, all tensile-tests are carried out at room temperature with at least five samples per set-up.

3.1 VARIATION OF RELEASE AGENT AMOUNTS

In test-series I the demolding stresses of RS II samples with IRA, ERA, and no release agents (NRA) are compared. In addition, different handling strategies are investigated by varying the number of applications for ERA, respective of the mass percentage for IRA. The ERA, therefore was applied with a microfiber cloth 3, 6, and 9 times. A pause of 10 minutes between each application ensures the evaporation of volatile matter. The IRA I and IRA II is added by 1.5% and 3.0% respective of the resin mass. The samples are cured in the oven at 90°C for 30 minutes.

3.2 VARIATION OF MOLD TEMPERATURE

Since the mold temperature is crucial during the injection in RTM processes [1] the sensitivity of demolding stress dependent on the application temperature is evaluated in test-series II. The pick-up plate with specimen adapters, is therefore heated to 50°C respectively 100°C in an oven for 1 hour prior to the application of RS I. After the resin application, an isothermal curing is performed at 50°C respectively 100°C for 15 hours. This temperatures is chosen to imitate an isothermal RTM process guidance.

Preliminary temperature tests with an infrared camera FLIR A325sc showed that the temperature drop during four minutes of resin application is not significant.

3.3 VARIATION IN NUMBER OF DEMOLDING PROCESSES

In test-series III the focus is on the development of the demolding force during a series of demoldings. The pick-up plate with specimen adapters is heated to 60°C in an oven for 1 hour. Both RS I and RS II are investigated and an amount of 3.0% of IRA I respective of the resin mass is added before mixing. The specimens with RS I are cured at 60°C for 15 hours. The specimens with RS II at 60°C for 1 hour. After the tensile-test, the specimen adapters are only cleaned chemically before another application of resin is performed. This procedure was repeated for three times.

3.4 VARIATION OF REINFORCEMENT STRUCTURES

In test-series IV the influence of different reinforcement structures is investigated. For this, samples with a diameter of 50 mm were blanked out of the raw material and stacked on the specimen adapters according to a lay-up plan (see Table 1). Subsequently, the pick-up plate, the specimen adapters, and the reinforcement material is heated to 60°C in the oven. Afterwards, RS II with 3.0% IRA I in respective of the resin mass is applied to the specimens and cured at 60°C for 1 hour.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 VARIATION OF RELEASE AGENT AMOUNT

The influence of different application strategies on the demolding stress is investigated in this series. The samples without release agent (NRA) show a demolding stress of 8.5 N/mm² with a standard deviation (SD) of 2,5 N/mm². The high standard deviation is due to the fracture behavior of the samples. Some specimens show areas with a fracture plane in the specimen instead of a release between specimen and specimen adapter surface, leading to destruction instead of a demolding. The demolding stress by the application of ERA is dependent upon the number of coatings (see Figure 3), where specimens with 3 and 9 ERA applications show lower stress values compared to the specimens with 6 applications. This coincides with Clarke et al. [8] who stated that thick release coatings can lead to high shear forces and therefore unstable demolding operations. The decline of demolding stress after 9 applications can be due to a reduction of the shear forces effect by excessive use of ERA. In the same way the demolding stresses of IRA I and IRA II depend on the amount of release agent. A higher

amount of release agent correlates with lower demolding stresses for both release agents. The lowest demolding stresses were observed at 3.0% of IRA I. The reason for the high standard deviation at 1.5% IRA I is not clarified yet, but could be due to an instable hand-mixing of the resin system and IRA I during preparation.

Figure 3: Demolding stress of NRA; 3, 6, 9 times coatings of ERA; 1.5%, 3.0% of IRA with RS II

For ERA it can be stated that increasing the number of application above three, does not lower the demolding stress. Further, three applications of ERA show the lowest demolding stresses in this investigation. In the examined range, the amount of IRA is indirectly in proportion to the demolding stresses. The highest amount of release agent showed the lowest demolding stresses. However, increasing the amount of IRA further, could not only decrease the demolding stress but could also reduce the mechanical performance of the resin system [9].

4.2 VARIATION OF MOLD TEMPERATURE

Both IRA I and IRA II show lower demolding stresses at higher temperatures of application and curing (see Figure 4). IRA I shows a decrease of demolding stress at 100°C of about 75% for 3.0% IRA I and 55% for 0.5% IRA I compared to the corresponding 50°C samples. The demolding stress of the 100°C sample of IRA II, equally, is 71% lower than the 50°C samples.

Figure 4: Demolding stress at different sample surface temperatures during RS I application

This corresponds with the statements of Critchlow et al. [2], that IRA are forced out during the cure of the resin system. Hereby, the higher surface temperature increases the mobility of the IRA in the

resin system. This is even more important for a small amount of IRA to ensure the drift of surface remote IRA to the surface. For a higher amount of IRA, the surface can be covered with less intense movement of IRA.

4.3 MULTIPLE DEMOLDING PROCESSES

In Figure 5 the demolding stress of both resin systems with 3.0% IRA for four demolding processes (DM) is visible. No surface passivation, i.e. lowering of the demolding stress, is visible over four subsequent demoldings. To the contrary, RS I shows an increase in the first three tensile-tests while RS II shows nearly constant values.

Figure 5: Demolding stress during four demolding processes (DM) without mechanical surface preparation

The reason for this behavior of both resin systems is not clarified yet. The increasing stresses for RS I could be due to a resin build up during the first demoldings, since no mechanical surface cleaning was performed between the tests. The high demolding stresses at the third tensile-test could indicate that the rest of the resin system was removed. By this, the lower stresses at the fourth demolding could also be described. Independently, both resin systems do not show a continuous decrease of demolding stress during the first demoldings.

4.3 VARIATION OF REINFORCEMENT MATERIALS

Figure 6 shows glass fiber reinforced material compared to the pure resin system both with 3.0% IRA II. The specimens with reinforcement structure show lower demolding stresses compared to the specimen with pure resin system and IRA II. Where the NCF and PW material show similar demolding stresses, the NOF shows higher demolding stresses.

Figure 6: Resin system with different types of glass fiber compared to the pure resin system

The NCF and PW specimens show similar demolding stresses. Even though the fiber volume content of PW is approximately 13% higher compared to the NCF structure. This could be an indicator, that the structure is more relevant than the fiber volume content. The higher demolding stresses of the NOF material could be due to shrinkage effects because of resin rich areas on the surface. Consequently, further investigations are necessary and will be done.

5 CONCLUSION

In this investigation the demolding stress dependent on process parameter is analyzed and three conclusions can be drawn. First, the IRAs show lower demolding forces for higher amounts of release agent, but no improvement was detected when increasing the number of applications of ERA. In general the ERA and IRA show demolding stresses of similar magnitude even though the IRA showed lower stresses at 3% mass percentage. Further, the temperature affinity of IRA I and IRA II is in compliance with the theory of a drift behavior of the IRA molecules based on an insolubility during the cure of the resin system [7]. Hereby, the higher temperatures lead to higher mobility of the IRA and lower demolding stresses. Finally, an influence of the reinforcement structure on the demolding stress can be confirmed, although the reinforcement material is not in contact to the tooling surface. The repetition of demolding tests without mechanical cleaning in between, on the other hand, do not show the expected results. Since the IRA is a component of the resin system, it was expected, that no release agent remains on the mold surface and therefore no change in the demolding stress is expected. While RS II shows quite stable demolding stresses, the reason for the increase of demolding stresses when using RS I is not obvious. Further investigations will be performed to clarify this issue.

Even though high effort was put on the repetition of the test results, the reason for the high standard deviation in some of the tests has to be investigated. One reason could be the mixing strategy, so that the distribution of 0,5g to 3g of IRA in 100g resin wasn't achieved homogeniously. For this reason, further investigations will focus on more efficient and reproducible mixing technologies. Moreover, the surface structure will be examined with respect to both the surface roughness as well as the sample adapter material.

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